

Green HR practices and green recovery performance in the fast food industry of Pakistan: exploring the mediating role of P-O fit and affective commitment

Samiya Hameed

Senior Lecturer, Business Studies Department, Bahria University, Karachi Campus, Karachi, Pakistan

Kehkashan Nizam

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Business Administration, Iqra University, EDC Campus, Karachi, Pakistan

Engr. Mahnoor Mujeeb

Lecturer at Food Sciences & Technology program, Department of Biomedical Engineering, Sir Syed University of Engineering and Technology, Karachi, Pakistan

Tanya Munir

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Business Administration, Iqra University, EDC Campus, Karachi, Pakistan

Adham Fayad

Assistant Professor, Doctorate of Business Administration (DBA), De Montfort University, UAE

Abstract: Environmental concerns are increasing and business firms are inclined towards adoption of eco-friendly products and services. They are hiring employees via set of green HRM practices and struggling to become an environmentally sustainable firm. Pakistani food industry is booming day by day. However, less is known about the green HRM practices executed in the fast food industry of Pakistan. Therefore, this research is interested in examining the impact of Green recruitment and selection, green training and development and green performance and compensation management on the P-O fit, affective commitment and green recovery performance in Pakistan's fast food industry. The moderating effects of transformational leadership will be examined between Green HRM practices and green recovery performance. A sample of 408 employees who are working at different designations were selected to accomplish the purpose of the research. These managers will be selected through convenient sampling technique. There were 21 fast food restaurants (Burger Joints) selected from all over Karachi, few of them includes; KFC, Burger Lab, Burger O Clock, Vintage, Plan B and more. The collected primary data will be tested through the application of structural equation modeling technique. Smart PLS software is used to assess the objectives. The results of the study revealed significant association between Green R&S, Green T&D and P-O fit. A non-significant association is found between Green P& C and P-O Fit. The study affirmed that Affective commitment posit a direct influence on GRP. The Green R&S and Green P&C revealed insignificant impacts on the green recovery performance within the fast food industry. The indirect association was analyzed between P&C, P-O fit, AF and GRP and revealed an insignificant result. Likewise, an indirect association is found between R/S, P-O Fit, AF and GRP. The future researchers are recommended to analysis the remaining elements of GHRM and investigate their impacts on the fast food industry of Pakistan. There is a need to create awareness regarding green HRM practices and their influence on the Green recovery performance in Pakistan. Policy makers are recommended to develop such policies that promotes GHRM in Pakistan.

Keywords: Green HR Practices, Affective Commitment, Green recovery performance, Transformational Leadership, PLS-SEM and fast food employees.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary business scenario, there is an increased inclination of environmental concerns and sustainable development, in both; developing and developed countries (Pearce, Barbier & Markandya, 2013). The global need to control climate change and generation of environmental management standards has enforced the business organization to embrace environment friendly or green practices (Sarkar, 2012). In the wake of rising environmental concerns, the business organizations are

now inclined to integrate the “Green Practices” to their human resource management systems. “Green HRM” refers to the implementation and execution of HRM policies in order to foster empirical consumption of resources within the business organization (Mandip, 2012; Wagner, 2013). This further assures environmental sustainability. Human resource initiatives are set to endorse eco-friendly practices and upsurge employee commitments and awareness regarding the sustainability concerns (Rani, & Mishra, 2014). Green HRM has two critical facets; HR practices that are eco-friendly in context and knowledge capital preservation (Zoogah, 2011). It aligns the environmentally friendly initiatives with the HRM practices, ensuring lower costs, higher efficiency, increase employee retention and engagement, assisting the organization to decline the carbon footprints.

Environmental concerns are rising and countries across the globe are aimed at structuring policies that could assist them in mitigating the environmental issues. For instance, in United Kingdom (UK), recruitment is affected by the environmental concerns. A study revealed that high-achieving employees evaluate the reputation and performance of the organization, before making decision of job application (Renwick, Redman, & Maguire, 2008). British Carbon Trust survey on 1018 employees in UK, revealed that 75% of the employees consider it significant, if the organization in UK has a policy for reducing carbon emissions (Renwick, Redman, & Maguire, 2008). Likewise, another survey by Chartered Institute of Personnel Development (CIPD) in UK showed that 49% of the sample was interested to know, whether the UK company has standards or policies for training and educating employees on adoption of green culture (Brockett, 2007). Likewise, a study conducted in Malaysian financial service industry revealed that GHRM practices are of considerable significance for the Malaysian firms (Ooi, Amran, Goh, & Nejati, 2017). The research was conducted on a sample of 504 individuals’ and found high perceptions about GHRM practices in the financial firms under investigation.

Luu (2018) claimed that the literature on green recovery performance is limited. He conducted research on some of the aspects of green recovery performance of the employees. Luu (2018) argued that the research on leadership based green recovery performance can add value to the existing literature. Luu (2018) recommended to investigate GHR based leadership styles and moderating roles of green recovery performance. The study by Luu (2018) thus revealed the need to conduct further research on green recovery performance and leadership styles related to GHR Practices. Currently, Pakistan as a country is far behind in understanding the need of Green HR practices in the fast food industry. Due to the rising environmental concerns Green Marketing is emerging. According to Malik et al., (2019), the general public is still unaware regarding green purchase. Tahir et al., (2017) recommended that HRM research and its implementation in Pakistan is the need of hour. The GHRM practices and awareness in developing countries is much higher than in Pakistan. Bhutto (2016) conducted a research on the Pakistani firms and investigated the impact of green HR practices on the performance of the firm. The author revealed significant influence of green training, green recruitment and green learning on the performance of a firm. The author recommended to conduct research on different green HR variables. Therefore, GHRM practices and green awareness are the two critical facets of the fast food industry that require critical research and consequent investigation in Pakistan.

Jabbar, & Abid (2018) argued that there is a glitch in the green HRM primary data availability in Pakistani fast food industry. Pakistan has a fragmented market of fast food industry. Unfortunately, the organizations in Pakistan are unaware that there is a concept of GHRM practices. There are substantial opportunities for the researchers, to tap this area of research. Hassan & Nawaz (2017) explained that the fast food industry of Pakistan is growing with a rapid pace. They investigated the association between ethical leadership, HR practices, SHRM and the performance of the organization. These relationships were identified in the context of indirect and direct trust. Another study conducted on Pakistani industry revealed the impact of green HRM practices in attracting the job seekers; however, this industry is different than the Pakistan’s food industry. Currently, less is known about GHRM practices in Pakistani fast food industry (Huma et al., 2017).

Three theories have been used to explain the relationship between GHRM & GRP namely; attribution theory, AMO (Ability- Motivation-Opportunity) theory and social identity theory. The core theories for current research are attribution theory and social identity theory. Luu, (2018) examined the green recovery performance and green HR practices. Luu, (2018) explained his research in the context of attribution theory and social identity theory. With reference to Luu, (2018) paper, both of the aforementioned theories are integrated in the current research investigation.

In accordance with the attribution theory, employees evaluate an organizational intentions and motivations via their perceptions of organizational practices and policies (Martinko, Harvey & Dasborough, 2011). Empirically, it can be argued that corporate social responsibility (CSR) is deemed as a macro-level bustle and employee’s perception regarding organizational social CSR policies namely; sustainability and social change, will influence behavior and attitudes of the employees (Dumont, 2015). In the light of attribution theory, it is essential to be aware of how employee perceptions get influenced by the cognitive (knowledge) and affective (attitudinal) processes (Dumont, 2015). The policies and practices themselves, does not affect employee motivation and behaviors, instead it is their perceptions

GREEN HR PRACTICES AND GREEN RECOVERY PERFORMANCE IN THE FAST FOOD INDUSTRY OF PAKISTAN: EXPLORING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF P-O FIT AND AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

that act as influencers. Reviewing the discourse between green HRM practices and employee work outcomes, attribution theory presents a rationale between employee perceptions about organizational green HRM practices and their consequent impacts on their behaviors (Sanders & Yang, 2016). For instance, if the employees develop a positive perception about organizational green HRM strategy i.e., taking care of the environment, then there is high probability that employees reveal positive behaviors and attitudes towards their respective organization (Dumont, 2015).

The intergroup behaviors relying on perceived legitimacy and perceived group status can be effectively predicted by the social identity theory (Shen, Dumont & Deng, 2016). This theory posits that employees struggle to accomplish and preserve a positive identity in their social circles (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). Social identity theory has recommended that the organization must focus on perceived green HRM practices. This enforces the employees to engage in the green behavior, and further identify, assess and then recompense the employees on the basis of their green contributions (Shen, Dumont & Deng, 2016).

Notably, the Green HR policies reinforce green behavior within an organization via the individual and collective capabilities of the employees (Norton et al., 2015). Through the implementation of these policies an environmental corporate culture can be developed. The employee's environmental behaviors are fostered through a set of organizational green HRM practices. These employees are influenced to adopt environmentally friendly consumption behaviors in their private life as well.

Prior research scholars in the Green management domain scholars argues that effective implementation of the Environmental Management System (EMS) can be effective when organization develop the capability to select right people with appreciable competencies and skills (Jin & Zailani, 2010). The execution of green HRM practices requires employees with higher level of management and technical skills (Teixeira et al., 2012). Therefore, there is a need to have an effective recruitment, selection, performance-based appraisal system, compensation, and training and development process aimed at creating environmental awareness among employees. Frontline employees create a perception regarding green performance of the organization. These perceptions influence their actions and abilities to mitigate environmental un-ecofriendly activities that are being performed by the organization, while they fulfill consumer demands. This green recovery performance is of considerable significance, as the employees take decisions based on their perceptions (Luu, 2018).

Problem Statement

The global fast food market is growing extensively and it has been identified that there is limited awareness of green HRM practices in this industry. Among the fastest growing fast food markets, Pakistan is recognized as one of them. The people of Pakistan are fond of socializing and visiting fast food outlets. The consumption of fast food is increasing with time and is becoming an attractive market for international fast food brands. Major market players in the fast food industry include; KFC, Burger Lab, Burger O Clock, Vintage, Plan B and more. These fast food chains are getting higher revenues from Pakistani market.

Research Objectives

The research objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To examine the impact of Green Recruitment & selection, Green Training & development, Green Performance & compensation, P-O-Fit, affective commitment on green recovery performance in fast food industry.
2. To examine the mediating effect of P-O-Fit and affective commitment between Green Recruitment & selection, Green Training & development, Green Performance & compensation and green recovery performance.
3. To examine the moderating effect of transformational between affective commitment and green recovery performance in fast food industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent times there have been wide discussions and a new phenomenon evolved that has been introduced as the Green HRM (Renwick, Redman & Maguire, 2013). This is said to be one of the emerging disciplines along with the beginning of Green Movement. It is particularly defined as the type of movement that can bring in four crucial elements such as; sustainability, social justice, environmentalism and non-violence. Those who support this movement are known as Greens and they have embraced the ideology of this movement and disperse ideas such as feminism, conservation, ecology and peace establishment.

The concept has been well recognized across the world, scholars of various disciplines; marketing, human resource, accounting and supply chain have initiated practices in the area of management that can make significant goal achievement. The United Nation Global Compact in alliance

with various educational entities has made the system known as Principles for Responsible Management Education which encourages the executives and scholars to work together on establishing the body of knowledge that can enhance environmental protection (PRME, 2010).

The initiative of such movement and their execution comprises of multiple units of an organization. The significant contribution of this is the HRM of the organization. The HRM discipline does not denote internal interest of stakeholders but acts as an important ingredient of competitive advantage (Wright, Dunford & Snell, 2007).

In the year 2000 Sutton, Griffiths, Dunphy and Beneveniste associated the execution of green sustainability with individual sustainability. The writers directed that investments and training in the field of human resources is kept aligned with the environmental sustainability. There are multiple organizations that are executing the pro-active approach in this stance and using a tool called EMS or environment management system to achieve the competitive advantage (Luu, 2018). This helps the management to control the impact of firm on the environment.

It is widely realized that the contribution of the employee within the execution of the EMS has a significant impact on the on its success. According to Sudin (2011), the positive impacts or the benefits of the green movement capital is visible in organizational environment which leads to a competitive advantage for firms. Hence, the HR role can be redefined to executives of environment from the HR personnel that can further lead to employee co-operation in executing the policies related to environment.

This research focuses on the rewards, empowerment and training modes of green HRM by considering the Babakus et al.'s (2003) report on the impact of HRM policies on recovery service performance. The argument of Nishii et al. (2008) concluded that the workforce behaviors are the type of response to HR policies and practices which are based on features they make related to management perceptions in HRM initiatives. Once the workforce receives the training related to green values they are empowered and are rewarded for making pro environmental contributions and are more effort makers to keep organization commitments to maintain green practices (Renwick et al., 2013, 2016).

There are some human efforts that need to be directed for making practices sustainable and to embrace these practices and these will eventually increase employee commitments. Green-HR comprises of environment friendly HR policies and conservation of knowledge. This means to consider the environment friendly measures with efficient means and low cost strategies, employee engagements and retaining them to assist organization to reduce carbon emissions (Luu, 2018).

The Green-HR practices emphasize the individual and collective abilities to embed green measures. Such initiatives are directed to maintain healthy organizational culture. Further such HRM practices focus on employee's responses in the workplace which are likely to determine their consumption practices (Muster and Schrader 2011). The researchers in Green HRM discipline have argued that EMS is effective and better to initiate if organizations and firms have right competent workforce with adequate skills (Daily and Huang 2001).

Green HRM practices may be inclusive of green training programs that create awareness, values, knowledge and attitudes regarding sustainable and eco-friendly concerns (Luu, 2018). Green HRM practices within the organization need to visualize the contribution made by their employees in managing the environmental sustainability. The organization need to identify and reward the employees. Employees who have done a remarkable environmental contribution in managing environmental concern (Bombiak & Marciniuk-Kluska, 2018)

The policies of green HRM are engrossed on individual and collective employee capabilities. Dumont, Shen & Deng, (2017) argued that environmental management systems (EMS) and initiatives enable an organization to recruit right employee for the organization, making a perfect person-organization fit. The implementation of Green recruitment and selection practices, performance based appraisal, compensation, training and rewards aligned with the aim to create environmental awareness.

In the light of the rising interest on this research topic, the study's aim is to comprehend how green HRM practices may lead to the frontline employees' enhanced green performance and search for a mechanism that contribute to the factors including: training, developing, selecting and rewarding for green behavior. Van Vaerenbergh and Orsingher (2016) has evaluated these HRM practices to have an effect of employee's loyalty to the organizations and eventually, the service recovery performance that they provide. In order to maintain and find out the link amongst these green HRM practices and green recovery performance, the research model will also examine the mechanism of employee environmental commitment (EEC) (Raineri & Paille, 2016). According to a research conducted by Raineri and Paille (2016) EEC can be described being a feeling of loyalty and dedication to environment in the workplace setting.

From previous literature reviews it has been established that transformational leadership is a very effective-model. It has been a significant amount of positive results at group-level of employees, it also has a positive impact on collective efficacy (Wang & Howell, 2012), effectiveness of groups as well as the citizenship of the organisation behavior, which all lead to a healthy team environment.

Ali, Islam & Parveen (2017) researched the effects of green HRM on potential job-seekers

GREEN HR PRACTICES AND GREEN RECOVERY PERFORMANCE IN THE FAST FOOD INDUSTRY OF PAKISTAN: EXPLORING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF P-O FIT AND AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

attractiveness on the markets of Pakistan. It also explored the important effect of the reputation of the employer on the link between green HRM and job-seekers attraction. A survey design was used to study a sample of 300 students that were in the last year of a Masters degree in Business Administration. These students were enrolled in three different universities in Southern Punjab.

The results of this research analyzed that the usage of GRHM practices directly effects the attractiveness of the organization on the job seeker. Moreover, it also showed that the reputation of the employer raises the positive influence of GHRM on the job seeker. This study has also paved way for further investigations in the field of green human resource management. It has also allowed the firms to come to a conclusion than the usage of green practices increases the green reputation of the organizations and also the attraction of the potential employees. In developing economies, the green human resource management is a new topic that has the attention of many scholars and consultants. Previously, there have been little research exploring the effects of green human resource management policies and procedures on the potential employees' attractiveness in Pakistan. The following research is based on a sample collected from different universities of southern Punjab, Pakistan. The study also concludes that the coming generation of Pakistan is a lot more considering towards the procedures and environmental practices done by companies (Ali & Ahmed, 2016). Keeping this context in mind, the study also concludes that GHRM practices such as the green recruitment, training & development, significantly impacts the intention of the potential employee to seek the job in a particular organization.

The research confirms the connection with the GHRM and the potential employee's attractiveness which is also on the basis of the reputation of the employer. The study depicts that the reputation of the employer is concluded on the various characteristics, quality, customer care, which influences the job seekers that are environmentally conscious. Comprehensively, the study comes to a conclusion that in Pakistan, the number of environmentally conscious job-seekers is rising

There has been no research relating the firms that practice GHRM in Pakistan (Ali et.al, 2017). Pakistani firms have no awareness regarding the factors of the existence of GHRM. There are a lot of opportunities that pave way for future researches on this topic. The topic for a research to be done in the future could be to determine the factors that are present for the very limited information about GHRM. The scholars can work on this area to gain create a wider knowledge-base for GHRM to be used generally. Future researches can also discuss on the introduction of elements that may, directly or indirectly, effect the environmental performance. Another tropic that can be done is the comparative study of GHRM between the countries that are developed and the countries that are developing (Jabbar & Abid, 2018).

Green recovery performance refers to the front-line manager's perceptions based on the organizational capabilities in managing the environmental concerns, on the road map to satisfy consumer needs (Zhu et al., 2016). Environmental concerns are increasing and firms are now making their services as environment friendly (Zhu et al., 2016). Employees are concerned about their social identity and have positive attitudes towards eco-friendly concerns. They thus apply in those firms that have an environment friendly focus.

The motivation behind the concept of Person-Organization fit is to promote the association between employee and the organization, in a manner that both gets satisfied, with their needs fulfilled (Kim, 2012). Employees get motivated, if their efforts are appreciated timely or their expectations get filled. In this case, the employees reveal higher levels of commitment towards the organization (Sharma & Dhar, 2016). In the perspective of green HRM practices employee reveal higher attachment towards the environmental sustainability objectives of the organization and assist the organization in accomplishing the sustainability.

Employees develop perceptions about the environmentally friendly activities owned by the organization and their practices and policies adopted in making the environment sustainable. The perceptions of the employees influence their behaviors and on the basis of positive perceptions, then apply for specific positions in the environmental sustainable firm. However, it is not only at the employee that develops positive/negative perceptions about eco-friendly behaviors of the organization (Luu, 2018). The firms look forward to recruit those employees that foster environmental sustainability and reveal positive attitudes and behaviors towards environmental friendliness. Therefore, P-O reveals a significant association with the green recovery performance of the organization.

Transformational leaders have the ability to inspire and motivate others through their personality traits of empowerment and delegation (Wang, Courtright & Colbert, 2011). In the context of Green HRM practices, transformational leaders act as moderators, in changing the perceptions of the employees about organizational environmental sustainability practices and policies. They engage the employees in green HRM practices; green training and green recruitment. These employees follow the instructions of their transformational leaders and reveal affective commitment towards the organization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For this study, quantitative approach was used. In quantitative approach a theory was adopted and hypothesis (or hypotheses) and then test those hypotheses.

The data was collected from primary respondents. Therefore, it was a primary research method which contains a questionnaire, based on quantitative already established scales. The data for quantitative questionnaire was collected by face to face interaction with the employees within the fast food restaurants. This will be an explanatory study which will test the relationship of the variables using the already established theories.

The research design used in this study is correlational. The correlational design explains the statistical relation between two or more variables as in the current research the Independent variables are GHRM Practices (Recruitment & Selection, Training & Development and Performance & Compensation) and dependent variable is Green recovery performance and we check the relationship between them. P-O Fit & Affective commitment are the mediators and Transformational leadership is the moderator.

The population of the study is the frontline officers of fast food restaurants in Pakistan. To select the sample from the population the combination of two sampling techniques; convenience sampling will be used. The first stage of selecting the sample from the population will be purposive or judgmental sampling. First line employees of fast food restaurants such as KFC, Burger lab, Burger'O Clock, Plan B etc. will be purposively selected for the study because the notion of green recovery performance and green HR practices is mostly prevalent in multinational restaurant chains where advance technologies are integrated so as to adhere to the challenges of green environment on their performance as well as customer satisfaction. Sample size is chosen by the help of number of observations required to complete a certain study a sample size is an essential aspect of empirical studies that has the aim to formulate supposition with regard to the population commencing a sample usually, N = 100–150 is regarded as the minimum sample size to conduct SEM (Tinsley and Tinsley, 1987; Anderson and Gerbing, 1988; Ding, Velicer, and Harlow, 1995; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2001). Some researchers consider an even larger sample size for SEM, N = 200 (Hoogland and Boomsma 1998; Boomsma and Hoogland, 2001; Kline, 2005). The sample size of this research will be 408 respondents due to the shortage of time and resources to reach the right population.

Questionnaires were filled by sitting in the fast food restaurants as well as in the head office sometimes from the sample size based on convenience sampling method. Established scales from previous studies are being used for collecting data. It contains 7 variables in total. Three Independent variables, one Dependent variable, Two mediators and one moderator. The questionnaire is in English and the instrument comprised of 49 items in total which comprised of three Independent variables, One Dependent variable, Two mediators and one moderator.

Affective Commitment

In order to measure affective commitment of front-line managers in fast food restaurants 7 item scale was created by Allen and Meyer, (1990). Responses were measured on likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree (1 to 5). Sample item include “I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization”.

P-O Fit

Six item scale developed by *Kristof-Brown, A.L. (1996)*, Cable and DeRue, (2002) to measure P-O fit. Responses were measured on likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree (1 to 5). Sample item include “I feel that my personal values are a good fit with this organization”.

Transformational Leadership

The transformational leadership was measured by using 18 items scale adapted from Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) by Bass & Avolio (1989). Responses were measured on likert scale ranging from the least to the most (1 to 5). This scale describes the perception of front-line managers for their Higher management. Sample item include “In my mind, the manager is a symbol of success and accomplishment”.

Green Recovery Performance (Service Recovery Performance)

Green Recovery Performance (Service Recovery performance) was measured from the 5 items scale given by Boshoff and Allen (2000). Responses were measured on likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree (1 to 5). Sample item include “Considering all the things I do, I handles dissatisfied customers quite well”.

Green Human Resource Management Practices (GHRM)

Green Human Resource Management Practices will be measured from the 13 items scale given

GREEN HR PRACTICES AND GREEN RECOVERY PERFORMANCE IN THE FAST FOOD INDUSTRY OF PAKISTAN: EXPLORING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF P-O FIT AND AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

by Guiyao Tang et al. Responses were measured on likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree (1 to 5). Sample item include of each sub variables are as follows:

- a. Green recruitment & selection, “we attract green job candidates who use green criteria to select organization”.
- b. Green Training & development, “We develop training programs in environment management to increase environmental awareness, skills and expertise of employees”.
- c. Green Performance & compensation “We use green performance indicators in our performance management system and appraisals”, “we make green benefits (transport/travel) available rather than giving out pre-paid cards to purchase green products” was measured using the scale of Guiyao Tang et al.

We will use Convenience sampling among 500 employees (front-line managers) of fast food restaurants which includes KFC, Burger King, Mc Donald’s, Pizza Hut etc.

Conceptual Framework

In this research, the statistical technique known as SMART PLS and structural equation modeling is employed to test the hypothesis as well as it is used to analyze the mediating role of P-O Fit & Affective commitment and moderating role of Transformational leadership and in order to address the objectives of this study we employed structural equation modeling. There are two steps to estimate SEM through Smart PLS 3. First step we use is model measurement in which we will test convergent validity and discriminant validity and second step will be Structural model testing in which we will test the hypotheses (path coefficients) mediation and moderation analysis.

It is the most general as well as powerful technique for the multivariate analysis. The technique of SEM is observed as the composition of regression or path analysis and regression analysis. This technique is helpful in determining the structural relation found between latent constructs and measured variable. Researchers usually in favor of this method because it can be easily measure interrelated dependence and multiple dependence within a one analysis.

RESULTS

Data Analysis

The PLS (SEM) is used by many research scholars to create statistical evidence and presents a rationale for research questions. It assesses the theoretical model that is proposed. The method is carried out with a specialized software called Smart PLS 3.2.3 (Ringle et al., 2014), and a random sampling has been done from subsamples of five thousand in amount (Hair et al., 2011; Raza et al., 2017a, 2017b). The PLS (SEM) is reasoned to be appropriate for numerous hypotheses and their deductions (Henseler et al., 2009) along with complex patterns (Chin, 1998a, 1998b). Furthering, the model is efficient and broad when compared with other techniques that are founded for covariance, such that it has the least constraints related to sampling sizes (Chin, 1998a, 1998b). Anderson and Gerbing’s (1988) talked about the steps in two points which was the foundation for the estimation. The reliability and validity was evaluated for the first step and for the second step, the valuation of the proposed hypothesis and the structured model was tested.

Table 2: Measurement Model

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>Loadings</i>	<i>Cronbach's alpha</i>	<i>Composite reliability</i>	<i>AVE</i>
<i>Po-fit</i>	PO-FIT1	0.758	0.785	0.786	0.684
	PO-FIT2	0.688			
	PO-FIT3	0.719			
	PO-FIT4	0.633			
	PO-FIT5	0.767			
	PO-FIT6	0.697			
<i>AC</i>	AF1	0.813	0.756	0.725	0.506
	AF2	0.792			
	AF3	0.645			
	AF4	0.844			
	AF5	0.675			
	AF6	0.671			
	AF7	0.685			
<i>GP&C</i>	P/C1	0.685	0.770	0.755	0.528
	P/C2	0.780			
	P/C3	0.822			
	P/C4	0.679			
	P/C5	0.624			
	P/C6	0.724			
	P/C7	0.625			
<i>GRP</i>	GRP1	0.859	0.925	0.919	0.663
	GRP2	0.918			
	GRP3	0.902			
	GRP4	0.860			
	GRP5	0.833			
	GRP6	0.809			
<i>GR&S</i>	R/S1	0.849	0.777	0.781	0.552
	R/S2	0.859			
	R/S3	0.756			
<i>GT&D</i>	T/D1	0.870	0.790	0.710	0.580
	T/D2	0.783			
	T/D3	0.777			
<i>TL</i>	TL1	0.647	0.910	0.785	0.659
	TL10	0.684			
	TL11	0.694			
	TL12	0.642			
	TL13	0.666			
	TL14	0.689			
	TL15	0.625			
	TL16	0.613			
	TL17	0.664			
	TL18	0.645			
	TL19	0.644			
	TL2	0.671			
	TL3	0.633			
	TL4	0.729			
	TL5	0.663			
	TL6	0.644			
	TL7	0.627			
	TL8	0.614			
	TL9	0.710			

A total of twelve assumptions were made by the researcher related to the study variables. The association between green recruitment & selection, green training & development, green performance & compensation and its impact on P-O fit was tested, respectively. The impact of P-O fit on the affective commitment was examined. The impact of affective commitment on green recovery performance was assessed. The moderating role of transformational leadership in the relationship between affective commitment and green recovery performance was analyzed. The research analyzed the impact of Green Recruitment & Selection (GR&S), Green Training & Development (GT&D) and Green Performance & Compensation (GP&C) on Green recovery performance (GRP), respectively, via hypothesis testing. This study examined the mediating effects of P-O fit and Affective commitment (AC) in the relationship between Green Recruitment & selection and Green recovery performance. Additionally, this study examined the mediating effects of P-O fit and Affective commitment in the relationship between Green

GREEN HR PRACTICES AND GREEN RECOVERY PERFORMANCE IN THE FAST FOOD INDUSTRY OF PAKISTAN: EXPLORING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF P-O FIT AND AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

Training & development and Green recovery performance. Lastly, this study explored the mediating effects of P-O fit and Affective commitment in the relationship between Green Performance & compensation and Green recovery performance.

Measurement Model

The convergent and the discriminant validity were used to ensure the accurate working of the model. The values of each variable were scrutinized in terms of their reliability, their composite reliability, the Cronbach alpha, and their average variance to evaluate convergent validity.

All the variables in Table 2 have a value of greater than 0.7 as their reliability, composite reliability and the alpha, it meets the given criteria (Straub, 1989). In the views of 0.55 should be the minimum figure for individual loadings as it ensures that the tool used is valid, and the ones discarded should be less than 0.4 (Churchill, 1979). Fornell and Larcker (1981) put forward that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) should at least be 0.5, and this was employed to test the convergent validity. All the variables met the standard suggested. After, an evaluation of the AVE cross loading was employed along with HTMT to test the discriminant validity.

Table 3: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Depicted in Table 3 in a negative sloping form are the square roots for the AVE, being above the correlation values for the individual items as specified (Fornell and Larcker, 1981), and hence meeting the standards.

Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	AF	GRP	P-O-Fit	GP&C	GR&S	GT&D	TL
AF	0.553						
GRP	0.098	0.814					
PO-Fit	0.380	0.214	0.699				
GP/C	0.324	0.600	0.302	0.798			
GR/S	0.425	0.487	0.384	0.780	0.743		
GT/D	0.504	0.444	0.544	0.268	0.348	0.693	
TL	0.506	0.521	0.682	0.705	0.636	0.404	0.584

Note: whereas, AF=Affective Commitment, GRP= Green Recovery Performance, PO-Fit=Person organization fit, GP&C=Green Performance & Compensation, GR&S=Green recruitment &selection, GT&D=Green Training & Development.

Table 4: Cross Loading

Similarly, Table 4 shows that each variable has a loading which is greater in their groups rather than if related to the variables held in other constructs. This in turn, elaborates the competence for the discriminant validity through the changes in cross-loading of more than 0.1, as was previously suggested (Gefen and Straub, 2005; Qazi et al., 2016)

	PO-fit	AC	GP&C	GRP	GR&S	GT&D	TL
AF1	0.529	0.813	0.150	0.001	0.317	0.182	0.277
AF2	0.543	0.792	0.173	0.152	0.170	0.154	0.255
AF3	-0.166	0.645	0.089	0.074	-0.074	-0.104	-0.177
AF4	0.592	0.844	0.220	0.153	0.274	0.200	0.425
AF5	0.376	0.675	0.173	0.139	0.324	0.181	0.370
AF6	-0.503	0.671	-0.131	-0.055	-0.291	-0.360	-0.422
AF7	-0.302	0.685	-0.058	0.071	-0.060	-0.338	-0.094
GRP1	0.204	0.091	0.297	0.859	0.269	0.039	0.246
GRP2	0.221	0.113	0.391	0.918	0.324	0.020	0.272
GRP3	0.147	0.056	0.473	0.902	0.396	0.030	0.261
GRP4	0.245	0.133	0.446	0.860	0.395	0.105	0.283
GRP5	0.214	0.089	0.413	0.833	0.356	0.053	0.211
GPR6	0.262	0.081	0.567	0.809	0.485	0.090	0.324
P/C1	0.168	0.063	0.685	0.327	0.549	0.366	0.272
P/C2	0.282	0.324	0.780	0.392	0.594	0.331	0.366
P/C3	0.261	0.215	0.822	0.423	0.585	0.206	0.455
P/C4	0.095	0.065	0.679	0.343	0.231	-0.013	0.172
P/C5	0.055	0.001	0.624	0.368	0.368	0.154	0.209

P/C6	0.121	0.088	0.724	0.335	0.311	0.134	0.141
P/C7	0.164	0.162	0.625	0.087	0.258	0.389	0.211
PO-FIT1	0.758	0.519	0.364	0.283	0.486	0.268	0.642
PO-FIT2	0.688	0.442	0.013	-0.013	0.146	0.452	0.344
PO-FIT3	0.719	0.511	0.253	0.275	0.198	0.332	0.449
PO-FIT4	0.633	0.346	-0.006	0.065	0.134	0.378	0.466
PO-FIT5	0.767	0.545	0.196	0.212	0.363	0.265	0.478
PO-FIT6	0.697	0.524	0.216	0.218	0.245	0.225	0.447
R/S1	0.303	0.309	0.605	0.411	0.849	0.393	0.364
R/S2	0.370	0.302	0.487	0.374	0.859	0.243	0.453
R/S3	0.257	0.224	0.525	0.300	0.756	0.252	0.370
T/D1	0.441	0.304	0.312	0.030	0.354	0.870	0.428
T/D2	0.309	0.255	0.189	0.078	0.223	0.783	0.406
T/D3	0.302	0.187	0.258	0.067	0.290	0.777	0.371
TL1	0.507	0.364	0.038	-0.009	0.379	0.370	0.647
TL10	0.409	0.277	0.287	0.165	0.277	0.219	0.684
TL11	0.452	0.313	0.140	0.092	0.349	0.324	0.694
TL12	0.345	0.368	0.060	-0.084	0.239	0.058	0.642
TL13	0.544	0.406	0.128	0.021	0.393	0.277	0.666
TL14	0.419	0.329	-0.003	-0.064	0.128	0.297	0.689
TL15	0.490	0.402	0.192	0.115	0.382	0.382	0.625
TL16	0.422	0.335	0.223	0.100	0.339	0.315	0.613
TL17	0.262	0.183	0.203	0.109	0.226	0.291	0.664
TL18	0.507	0.299	0.169	0.267	0.253	0.374	0.645
TL19	0.573	0.446	-0.066	-0.158	0.135	0.371	0.644
TL2	0.305	0.227	0.305	0.195	0.174	0.181	0.671
TL3	0.327	0.310	0.047	-0.016	0.043	0.273	0.633
TL4	0.558	0.358	0.255	0.166	0.458	0.356	0.729
TL5	0.583	0.440	0.156	0.110	0.282	0.358	0.663
TL6	0.451	0.267	0.249	0.143	0.326	0.384	0.644
TL7	0.576	0.537	0.281	0.051	0.458	0.328	0.627
TL8	0.521	0.422	0.213	0.115	0.278	0.407	0.614
TL9	0.468	0.355	0.272	0.150	0.257	0.384	0.710

Table 5: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Table 5 confirms that the maximum value for the HTMT (heterotrait–monotrait ratio of correlations) standard is 0.85 and all the variables measure less than that (Henseler et al., 2015; Raza et al., 2018).

The convergent and discriminant validity is hence, ensured by the calculative model and settles how it can determine the discrimination between variables. Therefore, it can be utilized to assess the model.

Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	PO-fit	AC	GP&C	GRP	GR&S	T&D	TL
<i>Po-fit</i>							
<i>AC</i>	0.846						
<i>GP&C</i>	0.355	0.338					
<i>GRP</i>	0.296	0.174	0.558				
<i>GR&S</i>	0.465	0.432	0.819	0.504			
<i>GT&D</i>	0.569	0.438	0.461	0.106	0.469		
<i>TL</i>	0.826	0.651	0.392	0.202	0.527	0.580	

Structural Model

To evaluate the structural model, standardized paths were scrutinized, where each standardized path corresponded to the relevant hypothesis. Further, it is then tested on factors of the dependent variable and the LV (Latent Variable) namely the size, signature, and the numerical significance found for the variable’s coefficient. The impact of the LV on the dependent variable is determined by the coefficient value, implying that if the significance is greater of the coefficient value, the effect would reciprocate. Considering the significance level of 0.05 for the testing, the outcomes are exhibited in Table 5. Green

GREEN HR PRACTICES AND GREEN RECOVERY PERFORMANCE IN THE FAST FOOD INDUSTRY OF PAKISTAN: EXPLORING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF P-O FIT AND AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

Recruitment & selection, Green training and development & Green performance & compensation has the positive effect on the P-O fit but the relationship is insignificant with GRS & GPC, while it is significant with GTD. The PO fit depicts significance as its effect on the AF is direct in nature. Affective commitment has a positive and significant relationship with Green recovery performance. GRS, GTD & GPC has a positive but insignificant relationship with GRP. Concluding, out of the twelve hypotheses, three were accepted and nine were rejected.

Table 6: Standardized Regression Weights for the Research Model

Hypothesis	Regression Path	Effect type	SRW	P Values	
H1	GR/S -> P-O-Fit	Direct Effect	0.215	0.169	Rejected
H2	GT/D -> P-O-Fit	Direct Effect	0.467	0.000	Accepted
H3	GP/C -> P-O-Fit	Direct Effect	0.009	0.949	Rejected
H4	P-O-Fit -> AF	Direct Effect	0.980	0.000	Accepted
H5	AF -> GRP	Direct Effect	0.140	0.001	Accepted
H6	GR/S -> GRP	Direct Effect	0.257	0.950	Rejected
H7	GT/D -> GRP	Direct Effect	-0.381	0.811	Rejected
H8	GP/C -> GRP	Direct Effect	0.234	0.988	Rejected

Table 7: Mediation Analysis

Hypothesis	Regression Path	SRW	P Values	
H9	GP/C -> P-O-Fit -> AF -> GRP	-0.001	0.999	Rejected
H10	GR/S -> P-O-Fit -> AF -> GRP	-0.029	0.977	Rejected
H11	GT/D -> P-O-Fit -> AF -> GRP	-0.064	0.980	Rejected

The guidelines provided by Nitzl, Roldan, and Cepeda (2016) for performing the evaluation for mediation concerning the practice of PLS was employed to test the mediation hypotheses. H9, H10 & H11 were rejected due to their insignificant relationship with GRP. Table 7 demonstrates the relationship between GPC & GRP, GRS & GRP and TL & GRP as insignificant in the presence of PO-Fit and AF. The insignificance of the values imply that full mediation exists (Nitzl, Roldan, and Cepeda, 2016) between the variables.

Table 8: Moderation Analysis

Hypothesis	Regression Path	SRW	P Values	
H12	TL -> GRP	0.190	0.934	Rejected

Table 8 shows that the P Value is 0.934, i.e. insignificant, TL does not moderate the relationship between AF & GRP

Discussion

Research shows that employers have a higher probability of hiring employees who are dedicated to work for environmental sustainability as GHRM recognizes Green recruitment and selection as a foundation.

The results of the study show that there is no significant impact of green recruitment & selection on P-O fit. It has been found that green training & development has a significant impact on P-O fit. The results of the study revealed insignificant results for the impact of Green Performance & compensation on P-O fit. The review of literature revealed that Green compensation encourages the employees to help the organization become an eco-friendly firm. The main principle of the green performance and compensation are within the green HRM concept and aligns employee goals with that of organizational objectives, furthering it as an immaculate PO fit (Luu, 2018).

This research presented an analysis of the Green HRM practices as green recruitment, green compensation, green recovery performance, affective commitment, P-O fit and determined their mediating and moderating impacts, specifically within the fast food industry. The results of the study affirmed the following results. Results of this study revealed that P-O fit and Affective commitment did not mediate the relationship between Green Recruitment & selection and Green recovery performance. Results of this study revealed that P-O fit and Affective commitment did not mediate the relationship between Green Training & development and Green recovery performance. P-O fit and Affective commitment did not mediate the relationship between Green Performance & compensation and Green recovery performance.

Obaid & Alias (2015) argued that it is essential to understand the scope of green HRM practices and their consequent impact on the firm performance due to several reasons. It influences employees to practice and maintain green behavior with the right HRM practices. Obaid & Alias (2015) argued that an

organization cannot perform well towards CSR, without corrective application of green HRM practices. Understanding depth and scope of GHRM practices and their role on green recovery performance is critical. The application of Green HRM practices can help in enhancing affective commitment amongst the employees and generating a P-O fit. The current research is focused on recognizing the influence of GHRM practices amongst fast food organization. This research presented an analysis of the Green HRM practices as green recruitment, green compensation, green recovery performance, affective commitment, P-O fit and determined their mediating and moderating impacts, specifically within the fast food industry. However, in this research, no impact of Green Recruitment & Selection on Green recovery performance was found and results are insignificant in nature. No impact of Green Training & Development on Green recovery performance found as insignificant results are obtained in the study sample. No impact of Green Performance & compensation on Green recovery performance has been found in the fast food industry of Pakistan.

The results of the study affirmed the following results. Results of this study revealed that P-O fit and Affective commitment did not mediate the relationship between Green Training & development and Green recovery performance. P-O fit and Affective commitment did not mediate the relationship between Green Performance & compensation and Green recovery performance. Evidence shows that the perception of the front-line managers on managing environmental concerns according to their organizations capabilities while meeting the standards for satisfying consumer needs refers to green recovery performance (Zhu et al., 2016). Potential employees that value their social identity and environmentally friendly concerns are more likely to apply to firms and organizations that have the ecosystem as one of their primary concerns.

According to Tan et al., (2018) there are three main aspects to green recruitment and selection; green employer branding, green attraction criteria and green awareness. The three main aspects help employers to analyze the candidate and evaluate if they are suitable for the job and foster the right PO fit. Additionally, green awareness helps the organization to study the personality traits of the candidate, optimizing selection and contributing to the central organization goals. Some of the factors that help in creating green awareness include green agreeableness, conscientiousness, and green consciousness. However, this study examined the association between P-O Fit and affective commitment and consequent impact on the green recovery performance. It has been found that P-O fit has the significant impact on Affective Commitment. Current study affirmed that Affective Commitment has the significant impact on Green Recovery Performance. The results of this research can be supported by the study of Suifan (2015) who affirmed that organizational commitment has a significant association with the human resource management practices as training, and rewards. The same study revealed that person-organization selection impacts the organizational commitment in a positive manner.

Sharma & Dhar (2016) explain affective commitment as a feature of commitment involving the relationship held between an employee and their respective organization. The relationship is crucial as it determines the retention of the employee and whether they would continue or discontinue their contract with the firm. This is demonstrated through an operative's emotional connection within the firm and consequently, through affective commitment. As an example, the depiction of an employee's level of responsibility, trust, and contribution towards balance and equity of the firm helps in the analysis of their emotional attachment and vis-à-vis their effective commitment towards the organization (Sharma & Dhar, 2016). Results of this study revealed that P-O fit and Affective commitment did not mediate the relationship between Green Recruitment & selection and Green recovery performance.

However, this research was conducted on the fast food industry and the results reveal that Green Recruitment and Selection, Green Training and Development & Green Performance and Compensation has the positive effect on the P-O fit but the relationship is insignificant with GRS & GPC, while it is significant with GTD. This is because, there are limited research investigations being carried out amongst the fast food industry of Pakistan. There are several challenges regarding green recovery performance and green HRM practices implementation in Pakistan. Although, this research contributes to the existing literature, however, there is still a need to create awareness regarding the green HRM practices amongst the fast food industry and their consequent influence on firm performance and green recovery performance.

Transformational leaders play a significant role in inspiring and motivating their colleagues and others through their natural traits such as empowerment and delegation (Wang, Courtright & Colbert, 2011). Green HRM practices recognizes transformational leaders as moderators, pertaining to the reason that they use their personality traits to influence and modify their employees' perceptions regarding organizational environmental sustainability. In taking initiatives as green HRM practices and green recruitment, employees engage in green training and green awareness. The transformational leader helps by influencing employees and subsequently, employees demonstrate affective commitment towards the organization. In the current research, Transformational leadership did not affirm moderating effect between Affective commitment & Green recovery performance as the results are statistically insignificant.

GREEN HR PRACTICES AND GREEN RECOVERY PERFORMANCE IN THE FAST FOOD INDUSTRY OF PAKISTAN: EXPLORING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF P-O FIT AND AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

Empirically, the notion of the PO fit surfaces on the foundation that the employee and the organization interact in a way that the needs of both the individuals is met in an optimal manner (Kim, 2012). In the case of employees, timely appreciation, recognition of their efforts, fulfilled expectations motivates employees and a higher level of affective commitment towards the firm is observed (Sharma & Dhar, 2016). Green HRM practices reveal that employees value the green initiatives that an organization undertakes and helps in the accomplishment of the green organizational objective.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Conclusion

The environmental challenges have enforced the business firms to engage in eco-friendly activities and work towards the sustainable development of the economy (Zoogah, 2011). These eco-friendly and sustainable practices usually named as “Green Practices” are gaining considerable significance across the globe. These practices enable a firm to become responsible and gain attention of their ultimate customers. The brand reputation is increased as the brand is inclined towards ethical and sustainable practices (Rani, & Mishra, 2014). This current research is focused in investigating the Green Human Resource Management Practices in the Pakistan’s food industry. The major players in the Pakistani food segment are inclusive of McDonald’s, Subway, Pizza Hut, KFC and Hardees. They have the concept of HRM but Green HRM practices in these firms are less investigated. The purpose of this research was to examine the impact of the Green HR practices, including recruitment & selection, training & development, performance & compensation on green recovery performance has been performed. The mediating role of P-O fit and affective commitment between Green training & development, Green performance and compensation and green recovery performance have been identified. The study also examined the moderating effects of transformational leadership between green recovery performance and affective commitment has also been performed. The research examined the impact of the aforementioned variables in the light of the Attribution Theory. The theory signifies how the perceptions of the employees are influenced by the affective and cognitive processes. The Green HRM practices performed by the organizations influences the employee’s knowledge and attitude in accordance with the attribution theory (Dumont, 2015). A Quantitative approach has been adopted for this research. The correlational study design has been chosen for the research. The sample was inclusive of first line officers working in Fast food outlets of Karachi; KFC, Burger King, McDonald’s, Pizza Hut and Subway. A sample of 408 participants were included in this research. The research included a questionnaire with 49 items having one dependent, three independent, one moderator and one mediator variables. The data was statistically treated with the application of structural equation modeling. This technique was helpful in revealing the mediating role of Affective commitment and P-O Fit as well as the moderating role of transformational leadership. The results of the study show significant results for Green training and development & P-O Fit, P-O Fit & Affective commitment, Affective Commitment and Green Recovery Performance via structural modeling. However, the mediation and moderation analysis revealed a p-value greater than 0.005. This means that the mediation and moderation analysis results are found to be statistically insignificant.

Practical Implications

Green HRM concept is a prevailing concept in the current era. The managers and employees are looking forward to firms that offer GHRM practices. These practices reveal that how responsible a company is towards recruitment, selection, policy making, compensating, etc. The organizations through their Green practices get a chance to build their reputation. These practices originate healthy organizational culture, with a minimization of waste and compliance with the ethics and moral principles. The current research has implications for fast food manager and future researchers. The association between P-O Fit and Green HRM practices as Green recruitment & selection, Green training & development and Green performance and compensation are significant from both the employers and employee perspectives. The role of the transformational leader in between this association of affective commitment and green recovery performance is of high worth. The employees that are joining the organization, they follow their leader and develops several perceptions regarding the green practices followed by the firm as well as the leader. On the basis of their perceptions, they then take essential decisions to be committed/not-committed towards the organization. Additionally, the Green HRM practices as observed by the employees and the development of the positive perceptions leaders to a perfect P-O fit. The results of the current study in the fast food industry of Pakistan, has justified that P-O fit and recruitment & selection green practices have a significant association. The managers need to understand that the green practices owned by their company will be helpful in attracting the right talent. Likewise, the significant association between Affective commitment and Green recovery performance in the fast food industry reveals that Managers must take care of the Green HR practices they are performing

within the fast food outlets. They need to assure that the practices are impacting the perceptions of the employees in the positive manner. They need to assure that the GHRM practices within the fast food outlets must benefit the society as well, in the social, economic and ethical contexts.

Limitations

The current research investigated the Green HRM practices and its impacts on the P-O fit, affective commitment and green recovery performance. The mediating roles of P-O Fit and Affective Commitment are examined and the moderating effects of transformational leadership in the association between affective commitment and green recovery performance has been visualized. The study has shown that the tools that are developed during the research study are reliable as the Cronbach Alpha's value is greater than 0.7. The application of Smart PLS and structural equation modeling are a strength for this research. However, the study was inclusive of a small sample size, and thus the results of the study may be inclusive of some biasness. Additionally, the researcher selected convenience sampling technique and visited the fast food outlets in Karachi only. This is another limitation for the current research. The researcher could have selected a greater sample and targeted the fast food restaurants of the country. Thus, the scope of the current research is found to be limited.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, S. (2015). Green human resource management: Policies and practices. *Cogent Business & Management*, 2(1), 1030817.
- Arulrajah, A. A., Opatha, H. H. D. N. P., & Nawaratne, N. N. J. (2015). Green human resource management practices: A review. *Sri Lankan Journal of Human Resource Management*, 5(1).
- Babakus, E., Yavas, U., Karatepe, O. M., & Avci, T. (2003). The effect of management commitment to service quality on employees' affective and performance outcomes. *Journal of the Academy of marketing Science*, 31(3), 272-286.
- Bagozzi, R. P. (1992). The self-regulation of attitudes, intentions, and behavior. *Social psychology quarterly*.
- Bhutto, S. A. (2016). Effects of Green Human Resources Management on Firm Performance: An Empirical Study on Pakistani Firms. *Eur. J. Bus. Manag.*, 8, 119-125.
- Bhutto, S.A., 2016. Effects of Green Human Resources Management on Firm Performance: An Empirical Study on Pakistani Firms. *Eur. J. Bus. Manag.*, 8, pp.119-125.
- Bombiak, E., & Marciniuk-Kluska, A. (2018). Green Human Resource Management as a Tool for the Sustainable Development of Enterprises: Polish Young Company Experience. *Sustainability*, 10(6), 1739.
- Brockett, J. (2007). Prepare now for big rise in 'green' jobs'. *People Management*, 13(10), 9.
- Brown, E. A., & Arendt, S. W. (2010). Perceptions of transformational leadership behaviors and subordinates' performance in hotels. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, 10(1), 45-59.
- Daily, B. F., & Huang, S. C. (2001). Achieving sustainability through attention to human resource factors in environmental management. *International Journal of operations & production management*, 21(12), 1539-1552.
- Das, Sudhir Chandra & Kumar Singh, Raj. (2016): Green HRM and Organizational Sustainability: An Empirical Review. *Kegees Journal of Social Science*. 8. 227-236.
- Demirtas, O., & Akdogan, A. A. (2015). The effect of ethical leadership behavior on ethical climate, turnover intention, and affective commitment. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 130(1), 59-67.
- Dubey, R., Gunasekaran, A., Helo, P., Papadopoulos, T., Childe, S. J., & Sahay, B. S. (2017). Explaining the impact of reconfigurable manufacturing systems on environmental performance: The role of top management and organizational culture. *Journal of cleaner production*, 141, 56-66.
- Dumont, J. L. (2015). Green human resource management and employee workplace outcomes (Doctoral dissertation, University of South Australia).
- Dumont, J., Shen, J., & Deng, X. (2017). Effects of green HRM practices on employee workplace green behavior: The role of psychological green climate and employee green values. *Human Resource Management*, 56(4), 613-627.
- Dumont, J., Shen, J., & Deng, X. (2017). Effects of green HRM practices on employee workplace green behavior: The role of psychological green climate and employee green values. *Human Resource Management*, 56(4), 613-627.
- Fast Food Market by Product Type (Pizza/Pasta, Burger/Sandwich, Chicken, Asian/Latin American Food, and Sea-Food) - Global Opportunity Analysis and Industry Forecast, 2014-2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/fast-food-market>
- Food Journal. (2016). Fast Food: Second Largest Industry in Pakistan. Retrieved from:

GREEN HR PRACTICES AND GREEN RECOVERY PERFORMANCE IN THE FAST FOOD INDUSTRY OF PAKISTAN: EXPLORING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF P-O FIT AND AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

<http://www.foodjournal.pk/2016/July-August-2016/PDF-July-August-2016/Exclusive-article-Dr-Noor-Fast-Food.pdf>

- Hassan, M. U., & Nawaz, M. A. 2017. Human Resource Management, Strategic Human Resource Management, Business Ethics and Organizational Performance: Evidence from Fast Food Industry in Pakistan.
- Jabbar, M. H., & Abid, M. 2018 A Study of Green HR Practices and Its Impact on Environmental Performance: A Review.
- Jabbour, C. J. C., & de Sousa Jabbour, A. B. L. (2016). Green human resource management and green supply chain management: Linking two emerging agendas. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112, 1824-1833.
- Jin, T. T., & Zailani, S. (2010). Antecedent and outcomes study on green value chain initiatives: a perspective from sustainable development and sustainable competitive advantage. *International Journal of Value Chain Management*, 4(4), 319-364.
- Kim, A., Kim, Y., Han, K., Jackson, S. E., & Ployhart, R. E. (2017). Multilevel influences on voluntary workplace green behavior: Individual differences, leader behavior, and coworker advocacy. *Journal of Management*, 43(5), 1335-1358.
- Kim, A., Kim, Y., Han, K., Jackson, S. E., & Ployhart, R. E. (2017). Multilevel influences on voluntary workplace green behavior: Individual differences, leader behavior, and coworker advocacy. *Journal of Management*, 43(5), 1335-1358.
- Kim, S. (2012). Does person-organization fit matter in the public-sector? Testing the mediating effect of person-organization fit in the relationship between public service motivation and work attitudes. *Public Administration Review*, 72(6), 830-840.
- Kooij, D. T., Jansen, P. G., Dikkers, J. S., & De Lange, A. H. (2010). The influence of age on the associations between HR practices and both affective commitment and job satisfaction: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 31(8), 1111-1136.
- Liden, R. C., Wayne, S. J., Liao, C., & Meuser, J. D. (2014). Servant leadership and serving culture: Influence on individual and unit performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 57(5), 1434-1452.
- Liu, B., Liu, J., & Hu, J. (2010). Person-organization fit, job satisfaction, and turnover intention: An empirical study in the Chinese public sector. *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal*, 38(5), 615-625.
- Luu, T. T. (2018). Employees' green recovery performance: the roles of green HR practices and serving culture. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 1-17.
- Luu, T. T. (2018). Employees' green recovery performance: the roles of green HR practices and serving culture. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 26(8), 1308-1324.
- Luu, T. T. (2018). Employees' green recovery performance: the roles of green HR practices and serving culture. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 26(8), 1308-1324.
- Mahmood, A., Sandhu, M. A., Kanwal, S., & Iqbal, J. (2016). The Effect of Green HRM Practices on Sustainability: Evidence from Manufacturing Companies in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)*, 36(1).
- Malik, M. I., Nawaz Mir, F., Hussain, S., Hyder, S., Anwar, A., Khan, Z. U., ... & Waseem, M. (2019). Contradictory results on environmental concern while re-visiting green purchase awareness and behavior. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 13(1), 17-28.
- Mandip, G. (2012). Green HRM: People management commitment to environmental sustainability. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*, ISSN, 2277, 2502.
- Mandip, G. (2012). Green HRM: People management commitment to environmental sustainability. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*, ISSN, 2277, 2502.
- Martinko, M. J., Harvey, P., & Dasborough, M. T. (2011). Attribution theory in the organizational sciences: A case of unrealized potential. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 32(1), 144-149.
- Muster, V., & Schrader, U. (2011). Green work-life balance: A new perspective for green HRM. *German Journal of Human Resource Management*, 25(2), 140-156.
- Nishii, L. H., Lepak, D. P., & Schneider, B. (2008). Employee attributions of the "why" of HR practices: Their effects on employee attitudes and behaviors, and customer satisfaction. *Personnel psychology*, 61(3), 503-545.
- Norton, T. A., Parker, S. L., Zacher, H., & Ashkanasy, N. M. (2015). Employee green behavior: A theoretical framework, multilevel review, and future research agenda. *Organization & Environment*, 28(1), 103-125.
- Ooi, S. K., Amran, A., Goh, S., & Nejati, M. (2017). Perceived Importance and Readiness of Green HRM in Malaysian Financial Services Industry. *Global Business and Management Research*, 9(4s), 457-474.
- Ostroff, C., & Bowen, D. E. (2016). Reflections on the 2014 decade award: Is there strength in the construct of HR system strength?. *Academy of Management Review*, 41(2), 196-214.
- Pearce, D., Barbier, E., & Markandya, A. (2013). Sustainable development: economics and environment

- in the Third World. Routledge.
- PRME. (2010). The 6 Principles for Responsible Management Education. Accessed online at <http://www.unprme.org/the-6-principles/index.php>.
- Ragas, S. F. P., Tantay, F. M. A., Chua, L. J. C., & Sunio, C. M. C. (2017). Green lifestyle moderates GHRM's impact on job performance. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 66(7), 857-872.
- Rani, S., & Mishra, K. (2014). Green HRM: Practices and strategic implementation in the organizations. *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, 2(11), 3633-3639.
- Renwick, D. W., Redman, T., & Maguire, S. (2013). Green human resource management: A review and research agenda. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 15(1), 1-14.
- Renwick, D., Redman, T., & Maguire, S. (2008). Green HRM: A review, process model, and research agenda. *University of Sheffield Management School Discussion Paper*, 1, 1-46.
- Reser, J. P., & Bentrupperbäumer, J. M. (2005). What and where are environmental values? Assessing the impacts of current diversity of use of 'environmental' and 'World Heritage' values. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 25(2), 125-146.
- Sanders, K., & Yang, H. (2016). The HRM process approach: The influence of employees' attribution to explain the HRM-performance relationship. *Human Resource Management*, 55(2), 201-217.
- Sarkar, A. N. (2012). Green branding and eco-innovations for evolving a sustainable green marketing strategy. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Management Research and Innovation*, 8(1), 39-58.
- Sharma, J., & Dhar, R. L. (2016). Factors influencing job performance of nursing staff: mediating role of affective commitment. *Personnel Review*, 45(1), 161-182.
- Sharma, R., & Gupta, N. (2015, January). Green HRM: An Innovative Approach to Environmental Sustainability. In *Twelfth AIMS International Conference on Management*. Retrieved from.
- Shen, J., Dumont, J., & Deng, X. (2016). Employees' perceptions of green HRM and non-green employee work outcomes: The social identity and stakeholder perspectives. *Group & Organization Management*, 1059601116664610.
- Steven Stern, (April 8, 2010) "Fast-Food chains adapt to local taste" Retrieved from: <http://edition.cnn.com/2010/LIVING/homestyle/04/08/fast.food/index.html>
- Sudin, S. (2011, June). Strategic green HRM: A proposed model that supports corporate environmental citizenship. In *International Conference on Sociality and Economics Development, IPEDR (Vol. 10, pp. p79-83)*.
- Suifan, T. S. (2015). The effect of human resources practices on organizational commitment: A Jordanian study. *Journal of Management Research*, 7(4), 222-232.
- Tahir, M., Rahim, Z., & Khan, R. A. (2017). Green HRM-Introduction, Predictors, Outcomes, And Future Prospects In Pakistan. *South Asia*, 1(1).
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (1979). An integrative theory of intergroup conflict. *The social psychology of intergroup relations*, 33(47), 74.
- Tang, G., Chen, Y., Jiang, Y., Paillé, P., & Jia, J. (2018). Green human resource management practices: scale development and validity. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*, 56(1), 31-55.
- Teixeira, A. A., Jabbour, C. J. C., & de Sousa Jabbour, A. B. L. (2012). Relationship between green management and environmental training in companies located in Brazil: A theoretical framework and case studies. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 140(1), 318-329.
- Uddin, M. M., & Islam, R. (2015). Green HRM: Goal Attainment through Environmental Sustainability. *Journal of Nepalese Business Studies*, 9(1), 14-19.
- Van Vaerenbergh, Y., & Orsingher, C. (2016). Service recovery: An integrative framework and research agenda. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 30(3), 328-346.
- Van Vaerenbergh, Y., & Orsingher, C. (2016). Service recovery: An integrative framework and research agenda. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 30(3), 328-346.
- Wagner, M. (2013). 'Green' human resource benefits: do they matter as determinants of environmental management system implementation?. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 114(3), 443-456.
- Wang, G., Oh, I. S., Courtright, S. H., & Colbert, A. E. (2011). Transformational leadership and performance across criteria and levels: A meta-analytic review of 25 years of research. *Group & Organization Management*, 36(2), 223-270.
- Wanshapala, G. G. M. A. P., Karunarathna, R. A. S. M., Mendis, B. C. P., Nadishani, H. A. S., Kaushalya, G. A. G., Perera, J. G. J. S., ... & Sandaruwan, S. A. H. (2016). Green Human Resource Management (GHRM). *The Junior Journal of Human Resource Management, Department of Human Resources Management*
- Wright, P. M., Dunford, B. B., & Snell, S. A. (2001). Human resources and the resource based view of the firm. *Journal of management*, 27(6), 701-721.
- Zhu, Z., He, J., Liu, G., Barba, F. J., Koubaa, M., Ding, L., ... & Vorobiev, E. (2016). Recent insights for the green recovery of inulin from plant food materials using non-conventional extraction

GREEN HR PRACTICES AND GREEN RECOVERY PERFORMANCE IN THE FAST FOOD INDUSTRY OF PAKISTAN: EXPLORING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF P-O FIT AND AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

technologies: A review. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 33, 1-9.
Zoogah, D. B. (2011). The dynamics of Green HRM behaviors: A cognitive social information processing approach. *German Journal of Human Resource Management*, 25(2), 117-139.